

Table S1. Trial Protocol: A Comparison of the Protocols of the Target Trial and Emulation of this Target Trial using Medicare Database

Protocol Component	Target Trial	Emulation
Eligibility criteria		
Included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age ≥ 65 • Diagnosed with T2D • Stable levothyroxine dose for ≥ 6 months • Willingness to participate and provide informed consent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age ≥ 65 • Patients with T2D • Stable levothyroxine dose for ≥ 6 months • Continuous Medicare A/B/D enrollment
Excluded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Had a previous history of any malignant cancer • Received palliative care, had a previous history of thyroid neoplasm, thyroid cancer, hyperthyroidism, thyroiditis, or thyroid disease • Took medication suggestive of thyroid diseases, can lead to fluctuations thyroid level, including amiodarone, tyrosine kinase inhibitors, immune checkpoint inhibitors, lithium, aminoglutethimide, interferon α, thalidomide, betaroxine, stavudine, prednisone, prednisolone, carbamazepine, phenytoin, phenobarbital, tamoxifen, PPIs, Calcium Supplements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same as Target Trial
Treatment strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Random assignment to GLP-1 RAs vs. SGLT-2is • Incident user for both group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalent-new user design • GLP-1 RAs (exposed), incident user • SGLT-2is (comparator), incident/prevalent user
Assignment procedures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1:1 randomization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1:1 propensity score (PS) matching using 24 baseline variables with caliper = 0.25 (logit of PS)
Follow-up period	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Followed from baseline (drug initiation) to 12 months or until outcome or dropout 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ITT: from index to outcome, disenrollment from Medicare, end of study, or death • PP: from index to outcome, disenrollment from Medicare, end of study, death, or discontinuation of levothyroxine
Outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time and frequency of TSH testing (lab test result) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time and frequency of conducting TSH testing (HCPCS code)
Causal contrasts of interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intention-to-treat (effect of being randomized to treatment) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same as Target Trial

Analysis plan

- Per-protocol (effect of receiving treatment strategy as specified in protocol)
- Kaplan-Meier curves for visual comparison
- Cox proportional hazards regression for time-to-event
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- Cox proportional hazards regression for time-to-event
- LASSO + logistic regression for predictor selection
- Sensitivity analysis using 1-SE rule (The largest λ ; Error is within 1 SE of the minimum error to perform a more parsimonious, less complex, and still perform nearly as well model)

Abbreviation: TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone; ITT, intention-to-treat; PP, per-protocol; GLP-1 RAs, glp-1 receptor agonists; SGLT-2is, sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors; HCPCS, Healthcare Common Procedure Coding System; T2D, type 2 diabetes; LASSO, Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator.

Table S2: ICD-9 /10 CM codes used to identify baseline characteristics and HCPCS codes used to identify outcomes

Baseline Characteristics	ICD-10	ICD-9
Atrophic Gastritis	K294.X	535.1, 535.10, 535.11
Bariatric Surgery	Z98.84, 0DB6, 0DB7, 0D16, 0DV6, 0DV7, 0DQ6, 0DQ7	V4586, 438.9, 443, 443.1, 443.2, 443.8, 443.9, 446.8, 449.5, 449.6, 449.7, 449.9, 449, 455.1, 459.0, 459.1, 436.44, 436.45, 437.70, 437.75, 438.42, 438.43, 438.45, 438.46, 438.47
Bowel Resection	0DT8, 0DT9, 0DTA, 0DTB, 0DTC, 0DTE, 0DTF, 0DTG, 0DTH, 0DTK, 0DTL, 0DTM, 0DTN, 0DTP	456.X - 458.X
Celiac Disease	K90.0	579
Cerebrovascular Disease	I60.X - I69.X	430.X - 438.X
Chronic Kidney Disease	E10.2, E11.2, E13.2, N00 - N08, N11, N12, N14, N15, N15.8, N15.9, N16, N18, N26, M32.14, M32.15, Q61.2 - Q61.9, Z99.2, D63.1, I13	250.41, 250.40, 249.40, 580.0, 580.89, 580.9, 480.4, 581.2, 581.3, 581.1, 581.89, 581.9, 582.2, 582.89, 582.1, 582.0, 582.4, 582.9, 581.0, 583.2, 583.89, 583.1 583.0, 583.4, 583.9, 583.81, 590.00, 590.01, 593.3, 593.4, 590.80, 590.9, 590.81, 585.5, 585.1, 585.4, 585.6, 585.9, 587, 405.91, 753.13, 753.12, 753.15, 753.16, 753.17, 753.19, 753.10, V45.11, 285.21, 404.01, 404.11, 404.91
Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease	J44.X	490.X - 496.X
Crohn's Disease	K50.X	555.0 - 555.2, 555.9
Dementia	F01.X - F03.X	290.X
Depression	F32.X, F33.X	296.2X, 296.3X, 29682
Epilepsy	G40.X	345.X

Family History of CVD	Z82.49	V17.49, V17.3
Food Allergies	Z91.01	693.1, V15.01 - V15.05
Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease	K21.X	777.8, 530.11, 530.81
Gastroparesis	K31.84	536.3
Heart Failure	I50.X	428.X
Helicobacter Pylori	B96.81	418.6
Hypertension	I10.X - I16.X, I67.4	401.X - 405.X
Primary Hypothyroidism	E01.0, E01.1, E01.2, E01.8, E02, E03.0, E03.1, E03.2, E03.3, E03.4, E03.5, E03.8, E03.9, E06.0, E06.1, E06.2, E06.3, E06.4, E06.5, E06.9, E89.0	240.9, 241.1, 243, 244, 244.1, 244.2, 244.3, 244.8, 244.9, 245, 245.1, 245.2, 245.4, 245.8, 245.9, 246.8, 780.01
Secondary Hypothyroidism	E23.0	253.2, 253.3, 628.1
Irritable Bowel Syndrome	K58.X	564.1
Ischemic Heart Disease	I20.X - I25.X	410.X - 414.X
Lactose Intolerance	E73.X	271.3
Osteoporosis	M81.X, M82.X	733.0X
Other GI	K57.X, K59.X, K64.X, K74.X, K80.X, K85.X, K28.X, K27.X, K20.X, K922, K2901, Z8711, K703, K717, P7881, K860, K861, K563	562.0, 562.00, 562.01, 562.02, 562.03, 562.1, 562.10, 562.12, 562.13, 578, 534.10, 534.20, 534.40, 534.60, 535.01, 533.00, 533.10, 533.20, 533.30, 533.40, 533.50, 533.60, 533.70, 533.90, V12.71, 455.0, 455.1, 455.2, 455.5, 455.6, 455.7, 455.8, 571.0, 571.1, 571.2, 571.3, 571.4, 571.40, 571.41, 571.42, 571.49, 571.5, 571.6, 571.8, 571.9, 577, 577.0, 577.1, 577.2, 577.8, 577.9, 574.00, 574.01, 574.10, 574.11, 574.20, 574.21, 574.30, 574.31, 574.40, 574.41,

574.50, 574.51, 574.60,
574.61, 574.70, 574.71,
574.80, 574.81, 574.90,
574.91, 560.31, 530.10,
530.11, 530.12, 530.13,
530.19, 564.00, 564.01,
564.02, 564.09

Peripheral Vascular Disease

I73.X

443.X

Rheumatoid Arthritis

M06.X

714.X

Ulcerative Colitis

K51.X

556.0X - 556.9X

Outcomes

HCPCS (Outpatient setting only)

TSH Testing

84443

T4 Testing

84439

Abbreviation: TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone; T4, thyroxine; ICD-9/10, International Classification of Diseases, Nine/Tenth Revision-Clinical Modification; HCPCS, Healthcare Common Procedure Coding System.

Table S3. Variables included in Propensity Score matching

Variable (Total number: 24)	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Age2. Gender3. Race4. Treatment Initiation Year5. Substance Use (tobacco)6. Substance Use (alcohol)7. Hypertension8. Chronic Kidney Disease (Exact match)9. Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease10. Irritable Bowel Syndrome11. Food Allegories12. Gastroparesis13. Ulcerative Colitis14. Crohn's Disease15. Celiac Disease16. Bariatric Surgery17. Other GI condition18. Family History of CVD19. Statin Use20. Number of Antihypertensive Medication (class)21. Number of Antidiabetic Medication (class)22. Charlson Comorbidity Index23. Cardiovascular Risk Score (QRISK3)24. Number of all-cause hospitalizations
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Table S4. Distribution and Timing of TSH and T4 Testing Within 1-Year Follow-Up

Total number of TSH testing	9,482
Total number of T4 testing	4,081
TSH testing and T4 testing at same day, Number (%)	4,052 (99.3)
T4 testing happened in 7 days after TSH testing, Number (%)	11 (0.3)
T4 testing happened after 7 days after TSH testing, Number (%)	18 (0.4)

Abbreviation: TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone; T4, thyroxine.

Table S5. TSH testing pattern and incidence rate of TSH testing among patients without chronic kidney disease and congestive heart failure.

	GLP-1 RAs (n=2,127)	SGLT-2is (n=2,127)	P-value
TSH testing 1 year before index date, Mean (SD)	1.9 (1.3)	1.8 (1.4)	0.0001
TSH testing 1 year after index date, Mean (SD)	1.6 (1.3)	1.5 (1.4)	0.0083
TSH testing 2 year after index date, Mean (SD)	2.9 (2.2)	2.8 (2.3)	0.0336
Days between treatments initiation and 1st TSH testing date 1 year after index date, Mean (SD)			
Days	133.6 (91.9)	129.5 (90.4)	0.2
Months	4.5 (3.1)	4.3 (3.0)	
Days between treatments initiation and 2nd TSH testing date 1 year after index date, Mean (SD)			
Days	218.9 (80.9)	216.4 (81.3)	0.5
Months	7.3 (2.7)	7.2 (2.7)	
Patients having TSH testing 1 year after index date, Number (%)			
No TSH testing	451 (21.2)	577 (27.1)	<0.0001
1~2 TSH testing	1,192 (56.0)	1,091 (51.3)	
≥ 3 TSH testing	484 (22.8)	459 (21.6)	
Patients having TSH testing 2 year after index date, Number (%)			
No TSH testing	279 (13.1)	399 (18.8)	<0.0001
1~2 TSH testing	783 (36.8)	706 (33.2)	
≥ 3 TSH testing	1,065 (50.1)	1,022 (48.1)	
Incidence rate, 1st TSH testing per person-year	1.6	1.4	-

Abbreviation: GLP-1 RAs, glp-1 receptor agonists; SGLT-2is, sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

Table S6. TSH testing pattern and incidence rate of TSH testing among incident GLP-1 RAs and SGLT-2is users.

	GLP-1 RAs (n=2,146)	SGLT-2is (n=2,146)	P-value
TSH testing 1 year before index date, Mean (SD)	1.6 (1.4)	1.6 (1.4)	0.7
TSH testing 1 year after index date, Mean (SD)	1.3 (1.4)	1.3 (1.4)	0.8
TSH testing 2 year after index date, Mean (SD)	2.4 (2.3)	2.4 (2.3)	0.8
Days between treatments initiation and 1st TSH testing date 1 year after index date, Mean (SD)			
Days	134.0 (92.6)	135.1 (91.5)	0.8
Months	4.5 (3.1)	4.5 (3.1)	
Days between treatments initiation and 2nd TSH testing date 1 year after index date, Mean (SD)			
Days	220.0 (79.7)	217.1 (82.9)	0.5
Months	7.3 (2.7)	7.2 (2.7)	
Patients having TSH testing 1 year after index date, Number (%)			
No TSH testing	746 (34.8)	764 (35.6)	0.8
1~2 TSH testing	992 (46.2)	981 (45.7)	
≥ 3 TSH testing	408 (19.0)	401 (18.7)	
Patients having TSH testing 2 year after index date, Number (%)			
No TSH testing	585 (27.3)	600 (28.0)	0.4
1~2 TSH testing	681 (31.7)	641 (29.9)	
≥ 3 TSH testing	880 (41.0)	905 (42.2)	
Incidence rate, 1st TSH testing per person-year	1.1	1.1	-

Abbreviation: GLP-1 RAs, glp-1 receptor agonists; SGLT-2is, sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

Table S7. T4 testing pattern and incidence rate of T4 testing

	GLP-1 RAs (n=2,685)	SGLT-2is (n=2,685)	P-value
T4 testing 1 year before index date, Mean (SD)	0.9 (1.2)	0.9 (1.2)	0.8
T4 testing 1 year after index date, Mean (SD)	0.8 (1.1)	0.8 (1.2)	0.8
T4 testing 2 year after index date, Mean (SD)	1.4 (1.9)	1.4 (1.9)	0.8
Days between treatments initiation and 1st T4 testing date 1 year after index date, Mean (SD)			
Days	143.4 (96.4)	141.7 (95.3)	0.7
Months	4.7 (3.2)	4.7 (3.2)	
Days between treatments initiation and 2nd T4 testing date 1 year after index date, Mean (SD)			
Days	225.1 (79.2)	216.9 (82.5)	0.1
Months	7.5 (2.6)	7.2 (2.8)	
Patients having T4 testing 1 year after index date, Number (%)			
No T4 testing	1,566 (58.3)	1,602 (60.0)	0.3
1~2 T4 testing	872 (32.5)	820 (30.5)	
≥ 3 T4 testing	247 (9.2)	263 (9.8)	
Patients having T4 testing 2 year after index date, Number (%)			
No T4 testing	1,291 (48.1)	1,325 (49.4)	0.6
1~2 T4 testing	806 (30.0)	794 (29.6)	
≥ 3 T4 testing	588 (21.9)	566 (21.1)	
Incidence rate, 1st T4 testing per person-year	0.6	0.5	-

Abbreviation: GLP-1 RAs, glp-1 receptor agonists; SGLT-2is, sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone; T4, thyroxine.

Table S8. Key Variables Identified by LASSO Logistic Regression (Using the Minimum Lambda Criterion)

Variable Selected	Coefficient	
	ITT	PP
Group	-	0.0260
Having TSH Testing During 1-Year Baseline	0.0981	0.0152
Age	-	0.0015
Gender	-	-0.0165
Race/Ethnicity	-	0.0093
Charlson Comorbidity Index (CCI)	-	0.0071
Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD)	-0.0038	-
Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease (GERD)	0.0315	0.0208
Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)	-	-0.0443
Depression	-	-0.0039
Ischemic Heart Disease (IHD)	-	0.0354
Peripheral Vascular Disease (PVD)	-	0.0219
Number of Antihypertensive Medication (class)	-0.0029	-
Number of Antidiabetics Medication (class)	0.0028	-
Heart Failure (HF)	-0.0125	-

Abbreviation: ITT, intention-to-treat; PP, per-protocol.

Table S9. Logistic Regression Results (Using the 1-SE Lambda Criterion)

Key Variables Selected by LASSO				
Variable Selected	Coefficient			
	ITT		PP	
Group	0.0000		0.0000	
Logistic Regression of Predictors of TSH Testing Within 1 Year, Odds Ratios and 95% CI				
	ITT		PP	
	Odds Ratio	95% CI	Odds Ratio	95% CI
Group				
GLP-1 RAs vs SGLT-2is (reference group: SGLT2-is)	1.07	(0.93, 1.24)	0.83	(0.73, 0.93)
Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD)				
Yes vs No (reference group: No)	0.88	(0.73, 1.06)	1.16	(0.99, 1.35)
Heart Failure (HF)				
Yes vs No (reference group: No)	0.76	(0.55, 1.05)	0.98	(0.73, 1.31)

Abbreviation: GLP-1 RAs, glp-1 receptor agonists; SGLT-2is, sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors.

Figure S1. Standardized Mean Difference (SMD) of Propensity Score Matching

Figure S2. Percentage of 1st and 2nd TSH Testing By Month During 1-year Follow-up

^a Given we depicted the TSH testing within a year, the sum of 1st and 2nd TSH testing may not be 100%, respectively.

Figure S3. LASSO Regression Selecting Penalty Term (λ)

^a $\lambda \text{ min}$: λ when the minimum mean cross-validated error was achieved.

^b $\lambda \text{ 1SE}$: the largest value of λ , when error is within 1 standard error of the cross-validated errors of $\lambda \text{ min}$.

Figure S4. Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve

A ROC Curve with Intention-To-Treat Method

B ROC Curve with Per-Protocol Method

